

Supplementary Information for:

Hällfors, M.H., Robson T.M., Burg S., Pentikäinen S., Koivusaari S. H. M., Luoto M., Nezval J., Pech R., Saastamoinen M., Schulman L., Sirén J., Susi H.: Thermal plasticity of multiple traits varies more within than between populations of *Plantago lanceolata* at its northern range edge.

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Figure S1. June and July temperature in Åland, Finland during 1960-2020 in relation to experimental treatments. The point and lines in light grey, grey and dark grey show minimum, median and maximum temperatures, respectively. The lines are smoothed conditional means fitted using *ggplot* in R (Wickham, 2016). The dashed horizontal lines in blue, peach and red show night (lower) and day (upper) temperatures set for the thermal experiments for the cold, mean and warm treatments, respectively.

Figure S2. Typical chromatogram of separated phenolic compounds obtained from HPLC-DAD analysis recorded at 270 nm. HCA – hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives; FLV – flavonoids.

Fig S4. Measured trait response across temperature treatment (summarized across populations) for A) leaf size, B) number of leaves; C) flower presence; D) number of flowers; E) flavonoid content of peak area mAU.s/ d.w. mg; F) HCA content; G) blue light reflection of inflorescence bracts; H) proportion of leaves with pathogen symptoms; I) number of individuals with or without PLCaV infection J) number of individuals with or without PILV infection; K) total number virus infections per individual (0, 1=either PLCaV or PILV infection; 2=both infections). Data presented per population in Fig S4. Estimated effects in main text Fig. 2 and Table 1.

Fig S5. Measured trait response across temperature treatment (separately per population) for A) leaf size, B) number of leaves; C) flower presence; D) number of flowers; E) flavonoid content of peak area mAU.s/ d.w. mg; F) HCA content; G) blue light reflection of inflorescence bracts; H) proportion of leaves with pathogen symptoms; I) number of individuals with or without PLCaV infection J) number of individuals with or without PILV infection; K) total number virus infections per individual (0, 1=either PLCaV or PILV infection; 2=both infections). Data presented per across populations in Fig S3. Estimated effects per population in Fig. S7.

Figure S6. Correlation plots of measured traits A) across treatments, and in the B) cold, C) mean and D) warm treatments. The correlation plots were created using the ggpairs function in the GGally package in R (Schloerke et al., 2024).

Fig S7. Posterior mean and credible intervals for the average response per treatment temperature and population (different colors). A) Leaf size, B) number of leaves; C) flowering probability; d) number of flowers, E) flavonoid content; F) HCA content; G) blue light reflection; H) proportion of leaves with pathogen symptoms; I) probability of PLCaV infection J) probability of PILV infection; K) probability of virus infections. Estimated effects (on the latent, i.e., modelled, scale) in main text Table 1. Estimated effects across populations in main text Fig 2.

Table S1. Information on seed sampling locations.

Population	Sampled individuals	Y-coord	X-coord	Location	Municipality
A	50	60.06770	20.071867	Söderby	Lemland
B	50	60.13275	19.989163	Österkalmare	Jomala
C	50	60.17423	19.523903	Skeppsvik	Eckerö
D	28	60.22434	19.559542	Storby	Eckerö
E	17	60.27522	20.240213	Hulta	Sund
F	39	60.25415	20.228615	Mångstekta	Sund
G	26	60.26042	20.178783	Strömbolstad	Sund
H	20	60.08355	19.906516	Gregersö, Möckelö	Jomala
I	48	60.06605	19.951663	Espholm, Ytternäs	Mariehamn

Table S2. Summary of model statistics for leaf size and inflorescence presence for models where one of the highly connected populations (E, F, G) was removed at a time. Part a) Mean of the posterior probability distribution with lower and upper credible intervals. Estimates are on the linear predictor scale. Part b) evidence ratio for a one-sided hypothesis asking what the posterior probability is of the response being bigger than 0 in the mean temperature, between the mean and the warm temperature, and in the warm temperature.

Response variable / sensitivity model	Estimate in cold (\pm CI)	Estimate in mean (\pm CI)	Estimate in warm (\pm CI)	Post. prob. of the resp. in the mean > 0	Post. Prob. of the resp. in the warm > 0	Post. Prob. of the diff. btw warm and mean > 0
Leaf size ($\sqrt{\text{cm}^2}$)	5.0 (4.6, 5.5)	5.5 (5.1, 6.0)	5.9 (5.4, 6.4)	0.96	0.99	0.93
Leaf size ($\sqrt{\text{cm}^2}$) E pop. Removed	5.01 (4.59, 5.51)	5.52 (5.04, 5.95)	5.91 (5.41, 6.36)	0.96	0.99	0.93
Leaf size ($\sqrt{\text{cm}^2}$) F pop. Removed	5.01 (4.59, 5.51)	5.51 (5.04, 5.95)	5.91 (5.41, 6.36)	0.96	0.99	0.93
Leaf size ($\sqrt{\text{cm}^2}$) G pop. Removed	5.05 (4.64, 5.44)	5.56 (5.15, 5.95)	5.92 (5.48, 6.32)	0.97	0.99	0.93
Flowering probability	-0.4 (-1.3, 0.6)	0.8 (-0.1, 1.7)	1.6 (0.6, 2.5)	0.97	0.99	0.93
Flowering probability E pop. removed	-0.30 (-1.15, 0.69)	0.87 (-0.04, 1.75)	1.55 (0.61, 2.45)	0.97	0.99	0.92
Flowering probability F pop. removed	-0.60 (-1.37, 0.34)	0.8 (-0.23, 1.54)	1.44 (0.48, 2.31)	0.97	0.99	0.93
Flowering probability G pop. removed	.042 (-1.33, 0.63)	0.66 (-0.32, 1.62)	1.52 (0.46, 2.47)	0.96	0.99	0.94

Table S3. Standard deviation attributable to the random effects for models on leaf size and inflorescence presence where one of the highly connected populations (E, F, G) was removed at a time. Residual SDs are presented only for the leaf size model where this parameter is well defined.

Response variable / sensitivity model	SD (\pmCI) attributable to <i>population</i>	SD (\pmCI) attributable to <i>mother ind.</i>	SD (\pmCI) attributable to <i>replicate</i>	Residual standard deviation
Leaf size ($\sqrt{\text{cm}^2}$)	0.1 (0.01,0.3)	0.2 (0.04,0.3)	0.3 (0.06,0.7)	0.6 (0.6,0.7)
Leaf size ($\sqrt{\text{cm}^2}$) E pop. removed	0.11 (0.01,0.28)	0.19 (0.04,0.30)	0.25 (0.06,0.75)	0.62 (0.55,0.71)
Leaf size ($\sqrt{\text{cm}^2}$) F pop. removed	0.11 (0.01,0.28)	0.19 (0.04,0.30)	0.25 (0.06,0.75)	0.62 (0.55, 0.71)
Leaf size ($\sqrt{\text{cm}^2}$) G pop. removed	0.14 (0.01,0.33)	0.19 (0.04,0.30)	0.22 (0.04,0.66)	0.63 (0.56,0.72)
Flowering probability	0.6 (0.1,1.2)	0.8 (0.3,1.2)	0.4 (0.03,1.2)	NA
Flowering probability E pop. removed	0.61 (0.14,1.21)	0.73 (0.22,1.17)	0.38 (0.02,1.15)	NA
Flowering probability F pop. removed	0.43 (0.04,1.01)	0.77 (0.33,1.19)	0.39 (0.02,1.19)	NA
Flowering probability G pop. removed	0.62 (0.15,1.25)	0.85 (0.41,1.30)	0.45 (0.03,1.25)	NA

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